

Development of Children's Mental Abilities Through Didactic Games on the Basis of the First Step State Curriculum

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Abstract: The first step in the article is the development of children's mental abilities through didactic games based on the state curriculum. The content of the article is aimed at the development of modern methodological approaches to the use of games in the mental development of children, the formation of cognitive competence, the organization of playful educational activities on the basis of games, and the development of the methodology of the content of mental development for children of preschool age today.

Key words: "First step", education, training, form, tool, innovative approach, excursion, mental development, intellectual potential, educational game activity.

Introduction

The state curriculum of preschool educational organizations is a normative-legal document developed in accordance with the "First Step" of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the State requirements for the development of preschool children, in which the goals and tasks of preschool educational organizations, the main ideas of educational activities, the main competences of preschool children in the transition to the next stage of education are determined.

Discussion and Results

Vocational education is the main form of teaching children in the organization. Training is a teacher's frontal awareness of the necessary knowledge and skills. The educator carries out education of children throughout the day: enriches their knowledge, develops various regional skills and abilities, such as cultural, hygienic, behavioral culture, speech, counting movements. But training plays the main role in education. Classes are a form of organization of education in a preschool educational organization.

The form of education means the specially organized activity of the teacher and the children and is held at a certain time in the agenda.

The form of education differs depending on the number of children, the nature of the interaction between the pedagogue and the children, the venue, as well as the place it occupies in the agenda.

Frontal (general), collective and individual forms of education are used in the organization of preschool education. In addition, children's education is carried out through excursions, educational games, during the day in various activities of children outside of training, in the process of guiding their games.

The lesson is mandatory for all children of preschool age: it defines the content of the program, a certain place and time is allocated to it in the agenda. The training is conducted under the guidance of an educator, the educator informs children of new knowledge, organizes practical training for children. The content of the educational material is gradually becoming more complex.

Education is of great importance in preparing children for school. Through training, children acquire educational skills. They develop abilities such as sustained attention, will, and the ability to attract attention. Interest in learning develops as a result of consistent teaching.

The game of preschool children is diverse. They can be classified according to the following types of games.

- 1) plot and role-playing games;
- 2) Dialectic games;
- 3) Games with action or rules;
- 4) Mixed games;
- 5) Seeing and creating games.

Kindergarten age is the main form of play for children with plot and roles. Children of preschool age play more interesting games such as "garden-garden", "train-train". But even if the games of children of different ages are the same, the plot is different. For example: while a small group of children play the game "kindergarten", they cook for lunch, cut bread, and wash the dishes. But cut bread is not given to dolls, cooked food is not served on a plate.

Didactic games play a big role in sensory education of preschool children. Didactic games are a great help to successfully conduct activities conducted on the basis of a special program in a preschool educational institution, and to prepare older children for school activities. Active or rule-based games are also important among children's games of preschool age. Because active games train children physically, encourage them to be brave, fearless, and agile. It inculcates the sense of initiative, team, and duty in children. This includes the games "Who's first", "ball", "white rabbit is sitting", "catch up". Action games are mainly held during walks and physical education classes. Dramatized games are also loved by children. In these games, various fairy tales and stories are staged, and the roles are performed directly by the children themselves. For example: "Little Red Riding Hood" and "Turnip" dramatic games develop children's speech, imagination and abilities.

Among the children's games of preschool age, construction games are aimed at a certain goal. Game activities allow children to learn individually. Some children like to play as a team, which affects the overall psychological development of the child. That is why educators should take the team to games. The role of the game in the development of the child's psyche is incomparable. It is difficult to imagine a child's mental development without play. Because through the game, the child develops not only physically, but also psychologically. Through the game, the child not only learns about the world, its events, and their characteristics, but also learns to speak, to think independently, to imagine, to be creative, and to learn the culture of behavior.

Many psychologists and pedagogues directly dealt with the psychological issues of the game and emphasized the importance of games in the mental development of the child. It is known that the game is a reflection of reality for a child. This reality is much more interesting than the reality that surrounds the child. The fun of the game lies in its ease of understanding. Just as activity, service, and work are important in the life of adults, play can be equally important in the life of a child. Based on the rich data collected in the science of world psychology, it is possible to reason as follows.

For example, games play a major role in shaping the most important aspects of everything from the simplest mental process to the most complex mental process. When it comes to the influence of the game on the development of movement in preschool children, first of all, it should be said that, first of all, the organization of the game itself creates the most favorable conditions for the growth and improvement of the movement of a child of this age. Secondly, the reason and feature of the influence of the game on the child's movement is that the subject learns the complex skills of movement not during the game, but directly

through training. Thirdly, further improvement of the game creates the most favorable conditions for all processes. Therefore, game activity becomes an independent goal that ensures the child's activity from a means of behavior implementation. Because it (the game) rises to the level of the initial object of the subject's (creature's) consciousness. A child of preschool age chooses a role with certain characteristics, and at the same time consciously strives to perform certain behavior characteristic of this or that character. Therefore, the game becomes the most necessary activity for this child, and the possibility of new forms of actions, improvement, and remembering them with awareness begins to become a clear reality.

Mastering these movements gives the child the opportunity to consciously perform physical exercises (A.V. Zaporozhets). The child's conscious goal arising from the conditions of the games is expressed when performing actions, and the goal he sets for himself turns into the processes of remembering and recalling. Compared to the laboratory conditions, the child has the opportunity to remember and recall more words in the games, which helps to reveal the nature of voluntary memory more deeply. Analysis of the data collected in the experiment allows us to draw the following conclusions:

- a) the process of choosing a certain role by the child in the game and performing it requires memorizing a lot of information;
- b) therefore, the conscious goal of mastering the character's speech and repeating his behavior appears in the child more quickly and is easily realized.

The game not only improves cognitive processes, but also has a positive effect on the child's behavior

According to Z.V. Manuylenko, who studied the psychological problem related to the development of self-control skills in preschool children, it is easier to acquire behavioral skills in a game than in a goal-oriented training. Especially, this factor is expressed in preschool children as a feature of their youth. Children learn to distinguish different colors and understand their differences through the game "Rainbow Bubbles". Through this game, children develop their imagination and distinguish the aesthetic placement of colors. That's why I tried to complete this game.

Conclusion

The importance of children's active activities in the game process for mental development is that children's various qualities and qualities are not only manifested in the game process, but it is necessary to realize that these qualities and qualities are strengthened and organize various games, especially the "first step" state. Based on the curriculum, it is possible to effectively use didactic games to develop children's mental abilities.

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